

Synthesis of 5-Dialkylamino-1-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-1-methyl-1-penten-3-ones and 5-Dialkylamino-1-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-1-methyl-pentan-3-ones

A. D. Palekar and R. A. Kulkarni

Synthesis of 5-dialkylamino-1-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-1-methyl-1-penten-3-ones (IV) and 5-dialkylamino-1-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-1-methyl-pentan-3-ones (V) as biologically active compounds is described. 1-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-1-methyl-1-buten-3-one (II) on Mannich reaction with paraformaldehyde and secondary amine hydrochloride furnished (IV), which on subsequent hydrogenation over Adam's catalyst afforded (V). Alternatively, (V) could also be synthesized through the application of Mannich reaction to 1-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-1-methyl-butan-3-one (III), the latter being obtained by hydrogenation of (II) over W_2 Raney nickel. The structures (IV) and (V) have been established on IR and NMR spectral studies.

Considerable work¹⁻¹⁰ has been done in recent years on the synthesis of various 5-dialkylamino-1-(substitutedphenyl)-1-penten-3-ones and 5-dialkylamino-1-(substituted phenyl)-pentan-3-ones in view of their spasmolytic,^{2,3,6,8,10} bactericidal,^{1,4,5,7} and analgetic^{3,9} activities. This prompted us to synthesize a series of 5-dialkylamino-1-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-1-methyl-1-penten-3-ones (IV) and 5-dialkylamino-1-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-1-methyl-pentan 3-ones (V).

The open chain ketone (m.p. 50-52°, 2 : 4 DNP, m.p. 132-34°), which was used as a starting material, has been assigned two different structures (I)^{11,12} and (II)¹³⁻¹⁵. The conclusive evidence for the structure (II) was deduced through NMR which exhibited a singlet at 7.75 τ (3H, $\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_3$), a doublet at 7.48 τ ($J = 1$ cps) (3H, $-\text{C} = \text{CH}_2$), a singlet at 6.20 τ (3H, $-\text{OCH}_3$), a poorly resolved quartet at 3.50 τ (1H, $= \text{CH}$) and two groups of multiplet at about 3.10 and 2.50 τ (4H, aromatic protons).

1. J. H. Burckhalter and S. H. Johnson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 4835.
2. S. B. Britton, H. C. Caldwell and W. L. Nobles, *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc.*, 1954, **43**, 641, 644.
3. B. Issekutz, J. Porszasz, L. Issekutz and K. Nador, *Acta Physiol. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1954, **6**, 95; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1955, **49**, 3394.
4. S. B. Britton and W. L. Nobles, *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc.*, 1955, **44**, 717.
5. W. L. Nobles and J. H. Burckhalter, *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc.*, 1958, **47**, 77.
6. T. N. Ghosh, A. Bose and A. Raychaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **36**, 319.
7. E. D. Taylor and W. L. Nobles, *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc.*, 1960, **49**, 317.
8. T. N. Ghosh, A. Bose and A. Raychaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **37**, 93.
9. C. D. Blanton and W. L. Nobles, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1962, **51**, 878.
10. C. H. Bruening, C. M. Darling, R. A. Magarian and W. L. Nobles, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1965, **54**, 1537.

Having confirmed structure (II), the synthesis of 5-dialkylamino-1-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-1-methyl-1-penten-3-ones (IV) (Table 1) was accomplished through the condensation of (II) with secondary amine hydrochloride and paraformaldehyde following the method similar to that of Maxwell¹⁶ or Pohland and Sullivan¹⁷. Formation of (IV) was ascertained through

their elemental analysis and IR spectra which exhibited sharp aband in the region 1685–1696 cm^{-1} , characteristic of β -aminoketones of type (IV)^{18,20}. The NMR spectrum of

(IV, $\text{N} \begin{matrix} \text{R}_1 \\ \text{R}_2 \end{matrix} = \text{N}^+ \begin{matrix} \text{---} \\ \text{---} \end{matrix} \text{O}$) disclosed a poorly resolved doublet at 7.40 τ (3H, $-\text{C}=\text{CH}_2$), a multiplet at 6.62 τ (4H, $-\text{N} \begin{matrix} \text{CH}_2^- \\ \text{CH}_2^- \end{matrix}$), broad multiplet at 6.34 τ (4H, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$), a singlet at 6.08 τ (3H, $-\text{OCH}_3$), multiplet at 5.75 τ (4H, $\text{O} \begin{matrix} \text{CH}_2^- \\ \text{CH}_2^- \end{matrix}$), a poorly resolved quartet at 3.30 τ (1H, =

CH) and two groups of multiplet at 2.95 and 2.40 τ (4H, aromatic protons). These pentenones (IV) (Table 1) upon catalytic hydrogenation^{1,6,8} over Adam's catalyst furnished corresponding 5-dialkylamino-1-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-1-methyl-pentan-3-ones (V) (Table 2) in good yields. The identity of (V) was established on the basis of elemental analysis and IR spectra which disclosed a peak in the region 1705–1710 cm^{-1} .^{20–22} Their NMR spectra were also consistent with the structures assigned. Pentanones (V) were also synthesized from ketone (III). Catalytic hydrogenation of (II) over W₂ Raney nickel gave (III) in quantitative yield. Its NMR, in addition to indicating the absence of an olefinic proton, showed the presence of CH- group (doublet at 8.78 τ , $J = 7$ cps, 3H) and also intact

COCH_3 group (singlet at 7.75 τ , 3H). Butanone (III) on condensation with paraformaldehyde and secondary amine hydrochloride^{16,17} gave desired (V) (Table 2).

11. G. R. Gogte, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1938, **7**, 214.
12. S. S. Karmarkar, *J. Scient. Ind. Res.*, 1961, **20**, 409.
13. D. B. Limaye and V. M. Bhawe, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1933, **2**, 82; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1934, **28**, 6128.
14. V. M. Bhawe, *Rasayanam*, 1938, **1**, 127; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1939, **33**, 1669.
15. J. J. Nerurkar and V. M. Bhawe, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, **25**, 1239.
16. C. E. Maxwell, *Org. Syntheses*, 1943, **23**, 30.
17. A. Pohland and H. R. Sullivan, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 4458.
18. R. B. Barnes, R. C. Gore, U. Liddel and V. Z. Williams, *Infrared Spectroscopy*, (Reinhold Publishing Corporation, New York), 1949, 21.
19. N. H. Cromwell, F. A. Miller, A. R. Johnson, R. L. Frank and D. J. Wallace, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 3337.
20. R. S. Varma and W. L. Nobles, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1967, **56**, 455.
21. H. W. Thompson and P. Torkington, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 640.
22. E. J. Hartwell, R. E. Richards and H. W. Thompson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1436.

Compound (IV) (Table 1) and (V) (Table 2) were screened for their *in vitro* antibacterial activity against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus albus* and *Agrobacterium tumerfaciens*. Of these, the MIC of 5-(1-piperidyl)-1-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-1-methyl-1-penten-3-one hydrochloride against *S. typhi* was 25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. Spasmolytic and analgetic activity tests are in progress and detailed results will be published elsewhere.

TABLE 1

Analytical data of 5-dialkylamino-1-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-1-methyl-1-penten-3-ones (IV)

Sl. No.	N	R ₁ R ₂	Salt	m.p./b.p. °C	S	Yield %	Molecular formula	N (%)	
								Found	Reqd.
1.		Dimethylamino	Base*	—	—	44	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ NO ₂	5.48	5.66
			Methiodide	144-46	a	—	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ NO ₂ .CH ₃ I	3.36	3.60
2.		Diethylamino	Base*	—	—	47	C ₁₇ H ₂₅ NO ₂	4.87	5.09
3.		Di- <i>n</i> -propylamino	Base*	—	—	46	C ₁₉ H ₂₉ NO ₂	4.76	4.62
4.		Di- <i>iso</i> -propylamino	Base*	—	—	12	C ₁₉ H ₂₉ NO ₂	4.48	4.62
5.		Di- <i>n</i> -butylamino	Base*	—	—	52	C ₂₁ H ₃₃ NO ₂	4.07	4.23
6.		Di- <i>iso</i> -butylamino	Base*	—	—	38	C ₂₁ H ₃₃ NO ₂	4.39	4.23
7.		Dibenzylamino	Base*	—	—	23	C ₂₇ H ₂₉ NO ₂	3.18	3.51
			Oxalate	158-60	b	—	C ₂₇ H ₂₉ NO ₂ .(COOH) ₂	—	—
8.		1-Pyrrolidyl	Base*	—	—	50	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ NO ₂	5.04	5.12
			HCl	89-91	b	—	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ NO ₂ .HCl	—	—
(Hygroscopic)									
9.		1-Piperidyl	Base*	—	—	62	C ₁₈ H ₂₅ NO ₂	4.82	4.87
			HCl	205-207	b	66	C ₁₈ H ₂₅ NO ₂ .HCl	3.98	4.32
10.		4-Morpholnyl	Base*	—	—	54	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ NO ₃	4.66	4.84
			HCl	193-95	c	60	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ NO ₃ .HCl	4.08	4.30

Satisfactory C, H analyses have been obtained for all the compounds.

* The product decomposes on distillation, hence purified by column chromatography over silica gel using benzene-chloroform (5 : 5) as eluent.

S = solvent of crystallization: (a) benzene; (b) absolute ethanol and (c) ethanol-acetone.

Refractive indices of compound (Base) Nos. 1 to 10 are n_D^{32} 1.5165, n_D^{32} 1.5420, n_D^{32} 1.5095, n_D^{32} 1.5105, n_D^{32} 1.5065, n_D^{32} 1.4975, n_D^{32} 1.5105, n_D^{32} 1.5235, n_D^{32} 1.5210 and n_D^{32} 1.5300 respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

Melting points and boiling points are uncorrected. IR spectra (thin films) were measured on either Perkin-Elmer Infracord or Hilger-Watts Infracan. NMR spectra were recorded on Varian A-60 spectrophotometer in CDCl₃ using TMS as an internal standard and chemical shift values are expressed in τ units. Kieselgel G was used for TLC while column chromatography was carried out on silica gel. Refractive indices were determined on Bosch and Lomb Abbe refractometer.

TABLE 2

Analytical data of 5-dialkylamino-1-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-1-methyl-pentan-3-ones (V)

Sl. No.	N R ₁ R ₂	Salt	m.p./b.p.°C.	S	Yield* %	Molecular formula	N (%)	
							Found	Reqd.
1.	Dimethylamino	Base	144-46/1.2 mm	—	50	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ NO ₂	5.46	5.62
2.	Diethylamino	Base	120-22/0.8 mm	—	44	C ₁₇ H ₂₇ NO ₂	4.92	5.05
3.	Di- <i>n</i> -propylamino	Base	117-19/0.7 mm	—	48	C ₁₉ H ₃₁ NO ₂	4.36	4.58
		Oxalate	212-14	<i>a</i>	—	C ₁₉ H ₃₁ NO ₂ ·(COOH) ₂ · 1.5 H ₂ O	—	—
4.	Di- <i>iso</i> -propylamino	Base	108-11/1.5 mm	—	14	C ₁₉ H ₃₁ NO ₂	4.28	4.58
		Oxalate	203-205	<i>a</i>	—	C ₁₉ H ₃₁ NO ₂ ·(COOH) ₂ · H ₂ O	—	—
5.	Di- <i>n</i> -butylamino	Base	178-80/1.2 mm	—	38	C ₂₁ H ₃₅ NO ₂	3.87	4.20
6.	Di- <i>iso</i> -butylamino	Base	160-62/1.2 mm	—	32	C ₂₁ H ₃₅ NO ₂	4.03	4.20
7.	Dibenzylamino	Base	106-108/1.7 mm	—	21	C ₂₇ H ₃₁ NO ₂	3.40	3.49
8.	1-Pyrrolidyl	Base	134-36/0.8 mm	—	52	C ₁₇ H ₂₅ NO ₂	5.14	5.09
9.	1-Piperidyl	Base	136-38/0.5 mm	—	58	C ₁₈ H ₂₇ NO ₂	4.72	4.84
		Picrate	162-64	<i>b</i>	—	C ₁₈ H ₂₇ NO ₂ ·C ₆ H ₃ N ₃ O ₇	10.83	10.80
10.	4-Morpholinyl	Base	168-70/0.4 mm	—	48	C ₁₇ H ₂₅ NO ₃	4.69	4.81
		HCl	157-59	<i>c</i>	—	C ₁₇ H ₂₅ NO ₃ ·HCl	4.04	4.26
		Oxalate	85-87	<i>a</i>	—	C ₁₇ H ₂₅ NO ₃ ·(COOH) ₂ · H ₂ O	—	—
		Picrate	186-88	<i>b</i>	—	C ₁₇ H ₂₅ NO ₃ ·C ₆ H ₃ N ₃ O ₇	10.62	10.76

Satisfactory C, H analyses have been obtained for all the compounds.

* Figures represent yields using method B.

S=Solvent of crystallization; (*a*) ethanol; (*b*) benzene—pet. ether; (*c*) acetone—isopropanol.

Refractive indices of compound (Base) Nos. 1 to 10 are $n_D^{25} 1.5460$, $n_D^{25} 1.5475$, $n_D^{25} 1.5390$, $n_D^{25} 1.5305$, $n_D^{25} 1.5645$, $n_D^{25} 1.5580$, $n_D^{25} 1.5185$, $n_D^{25} 1.5480$, $n_D^{25} 1.5640$, and $n_D^{25} 1.5660$ respectively.

1-(4'-Methoxyphenyl)-1-methyl-butan-3-one (III): A solution of 1-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-1-methyl-1-buten-3-one (II) (10 g.) in super-dry ethanol (40 ml) containing W₂ Raney nickel (5 g) was shaken on a low-pressure parr hydrogenator at 45 lb/sq.in. until one molecular equivalent of hydrogen was absorbed. Filtration of this mixture through silica filter bed and subsequent removal of ethanol left an oily residue which on distillation under *vacuo* gave (III) as colourless oil (9.5 g.), b.p. 110-12°/0.1 mm, $n_D^{25} 1.4885$. (Found: C, 74.88; H, 8.60. C₁₂H₁₆O₂ requires C, 75.02; H, 8.41%). 2:4 DNP of (III) was crystallized from ethanol, orange-yellow needles, m.p. 102-104°.

5-Dialkylamino-1-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-1-methyl-1-penten-3-ones (IV): (Table 1). A mixture of 1-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-1-methyl-1-buten-3-one (II) (3.8 g., 0.02 mole), appropriate secondary amine hydrochloride (0.02 mole), paraformaldehyde (0.9 g, 0.03 mole) and conc. hydrochloric acid (2 ml) in absolute ethanol (30 ml) was heated under gentle reflux for 24 hr.

It was then allowed to cool and then chilled in the refrigerator when solid hydrochloride separated. If no solid separated, the solvent ethanol was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was dissolved in water. The aqueous layer, after washing with ether, was basified with 12*N* aqueous ammonia to liberate corresponding base. The whole mixture was then extracted with ether and the ethereal extract after washing with brine solution was dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of ether left an oil which used to get decomposed during distillation and hence purified by chromatography.

5-(Dialkylamino-1-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-1-methyl-pentan-3-ones (V) : (Table 2).

Method A : A mixture of 5-dialkylamino-1-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-1-methyl-1-penten-3-one (IV) (5 g.), super-dry ethanol (40 ml) and Adam's catalyst (PtO_2) (0.1 g.) was shaken on a parr-hydrogenator under a pressure of 35–38 lb/sq. in at room temperature. After the theoretical uptake of hydrogen, the reaction mixture was worked up in usual manner to give corresponding (V).

Method B : Condensation of 1-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-1-methyl-butan-3-one (III) (3.84 g, 0.02 mole) with secondary amine hydrochloride (0.02 mole) and paraformaldehyde (0.03 mole) as described in the above procedure gave (V).

The authors wish to record their sincere thanks to Prof. T. R. Govindachari, CIBA Research Centre, Bombay, and Prof. R. E. Counsell and Mr. P. D. Desai, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, U. S. A. for NMR spectra, to Prof. A. B. Kulkarni, University of Bombay, Bombay and Prof. S. C. Bhattacharya, Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay for IR spectra and to Dr. Nitya Anand, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, and Dr. Jerome Korman, Upjohn Co., Kalamazoo, U.S.A., for pharmacological evaluation. One of the authors (A.D.P.) is grateful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, for the award of a junior research fellowship.

Department of Chemistry,
Ramnarain Ruia College,
Bombay-19.

Received July 20, 1970